

extracts of seed and leaf, growing on bioassay (GOB), and immunofluorescence staining (IF-S) using antiserum raised against *X. c. pv. oryzae*. Watanabe's medium was used for DP and DSP methods.

IF-S technique indicated the presence of the test bacterium in soil up to 1 mo after harvest (4 Nov 1985); negative results were recorded by DP and DSP test methods (see table).

X. c. pv. oryzae could not be detected

in stored seed lots by any of the methods. However, saprophytic yellow bacteria were found associated with the seeds. The seed did not produce diseased seedlings by GOB test and their extract (inoculation by tip clipping) did not initiate BB in 2.5-mo-old seedlings of rice TN1 in the next crop season, when conditions were congenial for disease development.

The presence of bacterium could be confirmed by all the methods in infected

leaves irrespective of storage conditions. BB could successfully be induced in seedlings of the test cultivar with a bacterial suspension obtained from the leaves.

These findings indicate that *X. c. pv. oryzae* did not overwinter in soil nor in seed collected from the diseased crop. Infected leaves seem to constitute the primary inoculum for the next crop season. □

Response of rice bacterial blight (BB) pathogen *in vitro* to antibiotics and fungitoxicants

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We tested the effect of 2 antibiotics and

In vitro bacterial inhibition efficiency of antibiotics and fungitoxicants at different concentrations against *Xanthomonas campestris pv. oryzae*. U. P., India.

Chemical	Concentration (ppm)	Mean inhibition zone (mm)		
		24 h	48 h	72 h
Streptocycline	1000	27.8	27.8	27.8
	100	25.8	25.8	25.7
	10	23.0	23.0	22.6
Thiram (75% WP)	1000	22.0	22.0	21.0
	100	17.0	16.5	15.2
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Streptomycin	1000	21.0	21.0	20.5
	100	16.0	16.0	15.0
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
MEMC	1000	18.0	17.8	17.3
	100	15.0	15.0	14.5
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Zineb (75% WP)	1000	18.0	18.0	17.8
	100	0.0	0.0	0.0
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Copper oxychloride	1000	17.0	16.6	15.5
	100	0.0	0.0	0.0
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Foltag (80% WP)	100	15.0	15.0	14.5
	100	14.0	14.0	13.0
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Carboxin (75% WP)	1000	15.0	15.0	14.0
	100	0.0	0.0	0.0
	10	0.0	0.0	0.0
Deltan (50% WP)	1000	15.0	14.0	14.0
	100	0.0	0.0	0.0
Captan (50% WP)	1000	0.0	0.0	0.0
	100	0.0	0.0	0.0

10 fungitoxicants on rice BB pathogen *Xanthomonas campestris pv. oryzae* using the paper disc assay method. Filter paper discs 12 mm in diameter, impregnated separately in 1,000, 100, and 10 ppm solutions of the chemicals, were placed on the surface of plated solidified and bacterium-seeded nutrient agar. Paper discs immersed in distilled water were the check.

One paper disc for each concentration of each chemical and for sterile distilled

water were placed in a petri dish. The experiment had three replications, three petri dishes serving as one replication. The plates were incubated at room temperature (30 °C ± 2). Zone of inhibition was recorded 24, 48, and 72 h after incubation.

Both antibiotics and seven fungitoxicants inhibited growth of *X.c. pv. oryzae* (see table); zineb, carbendazim (50% WP), thiophanate-methyl (70% WP), and sterile distilled water did not.

Streptomycin exhibited the widest zone of inhibition (27.83 mm) 24-48 h after incubation. It inhibited bacterial growth at all three concentrations. Thiram, streptomycin, MEMC, and Foltag inhibited BB at 1,000 and 100 ppm. Four other chemicals showed inhibition only at 1,000 ppm. Higher concentrations invariably increased growth inhibition.

Maximum growth inhibition by Deltan was achieved 24 h after incubation. Other fungitoxicants did not differ with incubation time. In general, the inhibition declined 72 h after incubation, except with streptomycin. □

Soil incorporation of fungicides to control sheath blight (ShB)

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Fungicides were evaluated singly and in combination under upland and lowland

Table 1. Soil incorporation of fungicides to control ShB on UPLRi 4 under lowland conditions. ^a UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease severity (%)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
Iprodione 50% WP	1	71.0	4.6 a
Benomyl 50% WP		74.9	4.5 a
Benomyl-EMDOC ^c	1	77.7	4.1 a
Benomyl-iprodione	1	72.9	4.1 a
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP-triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1	71.8	3.6 a
Triphenyltin acetate iprodione	1	74.8	4.1 a
PCNB	50	87.3	4.3 a
No fungicide (control)	-	90.0	3.7 a

^a Mean of 10 plants/treatment in 3 replications. ^b Sampling area for yield was 1 m². Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^c Ethyl 3-(3-5 dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-2-4 deoxo-5-oxazolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP).

Table 2. Soil incorporation of controlling ShB on UPLRi 5 under upland conditions. ^a UPLB, Philippines.

Fungicide	Rate (kg/ha)	Disease severity (%)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
Iprodione 50% WP	1	47.0	3.4 a
Benomyl 50% WP	1	50.7	3.1 a
Benomyl-EMDOC ^c	1	44.4	2.1 a
Triphenyltin acetate 60% WP-triphenyltin hydroxide 50% WP	1	48.8	2.9 a
PCNB	50	51.1	2.9 a
No fungicide (control)	-	57.7	2.4 a

^a Mean of 10 plants/treatment in 3 replications. ^b Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level. Sampling area for yield was 1 m². ^c Ethyl 3-(3-5 dichlorophenyl)-5-methyl-2-4 deoxo-5-oxazolidine carboxylate (Serinal 50% WP).

conditions during the 1983 wet season. Varieties were UPLRi 4 for upland and UPLRi 5 for lowland. Upland treatments (six) and lowland (eight) were in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Upland plots measured 2 × 3 m with 20 cm between rows; lowland plots were 2 × 2 m with 20- × 20-cm spacing. Fungicides were incorporated into the plots, and fields were planted the day after treatment. Plants were inoculated 45 d after fungicide application. Rice grain-hull culture of *Rhizoctonia solani* 3-4 wk old was inserted between tillers and between plants. Disease readings were taken 2-3 d before harvest on 10

random plants/plot and severity computed:

$$\text{disease severity} = \frac{\text{sum of disease rating}}{\text{total no. of rating} \times 9} \times 100$$

Under lowland conditions, all treatments except PCNB had significantly less disease than the control (Table 1). Under upland conditions,

Diseases of dry summer rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India

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Rice in the eastern part of Uttar Pradesh is mainly grown in the hot wet season 1 Jun-30 Nov. However, some farmers plant a small part of their holdings to rice during the hot dry season 1 Feb-15 Jun. Seedlings are raised while temperatures are still low. Although mainly dependent on irrigation, the crop occasionally receives one or two mild showers. It is harvested before the normal rainy season begins.

We surveyed farmers' fields in different districts and university experimental rice plots at Faizabad for incidence and severity of diseases in 1986 and 1987.

We identified bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, bacterial leaf streak (BLS) caused by *Xanthomonas*

Incidence and severity of major diseases in hot season rice in eastern U.P., India, 1986-87.

Disease	Disease incidence ^a (%)	Disease score ^b
BB	10-80	3-9
BLS	0-20	1-5
BS	0-20	1-3
Khaira	0-15	2-5
ShB	0-10	1-3
ShR	10-60	5-7

^a Based on percent leaves (BB, BLS, BS), percent culms (ShB, ShR), and percent plants (khaira) infected/unit area. ^b Standard evaluation system for rice, 1980.

plots treated with iprodione and benomyl-EMDOC had significantly less disease than the control (Table 2). In both situations, PCNB had the highest disease rating and disease severity. Iprodione and benomyl, singly or in combination, seem to control disease, although yields did not show significant differences. □

campestris pv. *oryzicola* (Fang et al) Dye, brown spot (BS) caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, khaira induced by Zn deficiency, sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn, and sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw.) Gams (see table). Incidence and severity of the diseases varied from cultivar to cultivar and field to field in both years. BB and ShR occurred consistently and, depending on conditions, severely. □

Virulent strain of rice grassy stunt virus (GSV) identified in Indonesia

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An unidentified rice disease showing tungro (RTV)-like symptoms was noticed in Java in 1981. We used a serological assay and transmission test to confirm its causal agent, a virulent strain of GSV.

Latex suspensions sensitized with antisera to GSV, rice tungro bacilliform virus, and rice tungro spherical virus were obtained from IRRI. GSV was detected by the latex test only in leaf samples collected from plants showing RTV-like symptoms at Cianjur, West Java. None of the samples reacted positively to antisera against the RTV-associated viruses.

Laboratory colonies of brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*